

Metaheuristic Feature Selection Optimization and Deep Learning for Breast Cancer Diagnosis

Hortence Ingabire

*Programa de Pós-Graduação em
Engenharia Elétrica e Informática*

Industrial

Universidade Tecnológica Federal do

Paraná (UTFPR)

Curitiba, Brazil

ORCID: 0000-0002-8471-4769

Lúcia Valéria Ramos de
Arruda

*Programa de Pós-Graduação em
Engenharia Elétrica e Informática*

Industrial

Universidade Tecnológica Federal do

Paraná (UTFPR)

Curitiba, Brazil

ORCID: 0000-0002-5704-8131

Abstract— Breast cancer remains a leading cause of global mortality, emphasizing the need for accurate early diagnosis. This study proposes a hybrid diagnostic approach that combines metaheuristic feature selection with deep learning to improve classification performance. Using the Breast Cancer Wisconsin dataset, two metaheuristics techniques, Ant Colony Optimization (ACO) and Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) were evaluated for selecting informative features. PSO achieved superior results, selecting 11 out of 30 features and attaining 100% accuracy, outperforming ACO's 98.2%. Feature subsets were evaluated using a Random Forest classifier to guide selection. These optimized features were then used to train deep learning classification models, including Convolutional Neural Network (CNN), Gated Recurrent Unit (GRU), and hybrid CNN-GRU. The CNN-GRU achieved the best performance with 99.1% accuracy and near-perfect precision, recall, and F1-score. This integration of metaheuristics and deep learning demonstrates a promising framework for robust, high-accuracy breast cancer diagnosis. It offers a scalable, intelligent approach for managing high-dimensional biomedical data, contributing to early disease detection and addressing critical public health challenges.

Keywords— Breast Cancer, Metaheuristic Optimization, Feature Selection, Deep Learning, CNN-GRU.

I. INTRODUCTION

Breast cancer is the most common cancer among women worldwide and a leading cause of cancer mortality [1, 2]. In 2022, there were approximately 2.3 million new cases and 670,000 deaths globally, representing 11.6% and 6.9% of all cancers, respectively [1, 3, 4]. Projections suggest cases will rise to 3.2 million and deaths to 1.1 million by 2050 [4, 5]. In Brazil, breast cancer is also the most prevalent female cancer, with about 73,610 new cases annually and a 66.5 per 100,000 incidence rate from 2023–2025 [6, 7]. Nearly 40% of patients are diagnosed at advanced stages, underscoring diagnostic challenges [7]. High-dimensional biomedical data often contain redundant or irrelevant features [8], which can impair

deep learning models by increasing overfitting risk, computational load, and reducing generalization [9, 10].

Feature Subset Selection (FSS) reduces dimensionality by selecting relevant features, improving interpretability, training efficiency, and predictive performance [10, 12, 13]. FSS is critical in biomedical applications including gene identification and cancer diagnosis [8, 9, 10, 11, 12]. Metaheuristic algorithms inspired by nature, such as Ant Colony Optimization (ACO) and Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO), have demonstrated effectiveness in high-dimensional FS problems [8, 10, 15]. These methods explore complex search spaces, avoid local optima, and reduce feature set size, aiding data analysis [12, 13, 14].

FSS methods are selection-based, which retain original features, or transformation-based, which create new ones [10]. This study adopts a selection-based wrapper approach [10, 11], using Random Forest (RF) as the evaluation metric due to its robustness against noise, overfitting [21, 22] and ability to handle imbalanced medical data [22, 23]. The goal is to maximize accuracy while minimizing selected features [12, 14], a multi-objective optimization problem well-suited to metaheuristics [10, 11, 12]. Deep learning models like Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) and Gated Recurrent Units (GRUs) are effective for spatial and sequential biomedical data, respectively [16, 18, 19]. Hybrid CNN-GRU architectures further enhance classification performance by combining strengths of both models [17, 19]. Due to infeasibility of exhaustive feature search in complex datasets, metaheuristic feature selection combined with hybrid deep learning models offers scalable, accurate solutions for breast cancer diagnosis.

This work proposes a wrapper-based feature selection framework integrating ACO and PSO with RF evaluation to reduce dimensionality and improve breast cancer classification with deep learning. The method provides a robust, scalable approach for complex biomedical data analysis.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

In this work, the methodology has four key sections: (i) Overview of the proposed approach, (ii) Dataset description and preprocessing, (iii) Model architecture and evaluation, and (iv) Hyperparameter settings and experimental setup.

A. Overview of the proposed approach

As illustrated in Fig. 1, the workflow began with preprocessing the Breast Cancer Wisconsin (Diagnostic) dataset. After normalization and label encoding, the data was split (80% training, 20% testing). Feature selection was performed using two metaheuristic algorithms, Ant Colony Optimization and Particle Swarm Optimization within a wrapper-based framework. A Random Forest (RF) classifier guided the feature selection as the fitness evaluator. Both algorithms iteratively refined populations of candidate feature subsets. Upon convergence, PSO demonstrated superior performance in both accuracy and subset compactness. The best PSO-selected features were used to train three deep learning models: CNN, GRU, and CNN-GRU. Outputs include class predictions (benign/malignant) and evaluation metrics such as accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score.

B. Dataset description and preprocessing

The Breast Cancer Wisconsin (Diagnostic) dataset was obtained from Kaggle repository [3, 20], comprising 569 samples with 30 real-valued features and two classes: Benign (357) and Malignant (212). No missing data was present, and each feature represents a specific characteristic of the cell nuclei (e.g., radius, texture, smoothness). Features were scaled to [0, 1] using min-max normalization, and class labels were encoded (Malignant = 1, Benign = 0). The dataset (raw and reduced dataset) was split into 80% training and 20% testing, maintaining the original class distribution. The training set was used to fit the models, while the testing set served to evaluate their performance.

C. Model architecture and evaluation

1. ACO and PSO for Feature Selection

ACO and PSO were employed to identify optimal feature subsets. ACO was inspired by the pheromone-based foraging behavior of ants, where feature subsets were constructed based on pheromone intensity and heuristic information. Pheromone trails were updated according to the classification accuracy obtained from a RF classifier, guiding the search toward the most informative features. PSO, on the other hand, mimicked the social behavior of bird flocks,

Fig. 1 Workflow of the proposed algorithm

representing feature subsets as binary vectors. These vectors were iteratively updated using both personal and global best solutions, with a sigmoid transfer function applied to maintain binary encoding. The FS procedures using ACO and PSO were implemented as proposed in [9]-[12].

In both algorithms, fitness evaluation was carried out using a Random Forest classifier with 100 estimators. The accuracy on the test set served as the fitness metric, guiding the search toward more informative and discriminative features. RF was chosen due to its robustness, generalization ability, and proven performance on medical datasets. Its ability to generalize well to unseen data, even with minimal parameter tuning, made it a suitable choice for guiding the metaheuristic search. This approach provided a consistent and computationally efficient method for evaluating the quality of feature subsets throughout the optimization process. The algorithm that produced the feature subset with the highest accuracy, as determined by the RF fitness evaluation, was considered the best-performing method. This optimal subset was then used to train the deep learning classifiers.

2. Deep learning classification

PSO-selected features were used to train three deep learning models, CNN, GRU and CNN-GRU. The optimized dataset was split into 80% training and 20% testing sets. Fig. 2-4 shows the models architecture. This strategy ensured that deep learning models were trained on the most relevant features, promoting generalization and reducing the risk of overfitting.

- **CNN architecture:** The CNN architecture began with a one-dimensional convolutional layer (Conv1D) consisting of 64 filters with a kernel size of 3 and ReLU activation to extract spatial features. This was followed by a max pooling layer (pool size of 2) and a dropout layer (dropout rate of 0.3). The output was flattened and passed through two dense layers: one with 32 units (ReLU) and a final output layer with 2 units and softmax activation for binary classification.

- **GRU architecture:** The GRU model utilized a Gated Recurrent Unit layer with 64 units and ReLU activation to capture temporal dependencies. A dropout layer with a rate of 0.3 was added to prevent overfitting. The GRU output was fed into a dense layer with 32 ReLU-activated units and a final softmax layer with 2 units for classification.

- **CNN-GRU hybrid architecture:** This model combined both spatial and sequential learning. It began with a Conv1D layer (64 filters, kernel size 3, ReLU), followed by max pooling and a GRU layer with 64 units for temporal modeling. To prevent overfitting, a dropout layer (rate = 0.3) is applied after the GRU, followed by a dense layer (32 ReLU units) and a softmax output layer with 2 units for binary classification.

Fig. 2 CNN architecture

Fig. 3 GRU architecture

The evaluation metrics for the three deep learning models were accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score [3].

- **Accuracy:** Represents the proportion of correctly classified samples among all instances.

$$\text{Accuracy} = \frac{TP+TN}{TP+TN+FP+FN} \quad (1)$$

- **Precision:** Indicates the proportion of true positive predictions among all positive predictions.

$$\text{Precision} = \frac{TP}{TP+FP} \quad (2)$$

- **Recall:** Measures the proportion of true positive instances correctly identified, assessing the model's sensitivity to positive cases.

$$\text{Recall} = \frac{TP}{TP+FN} \quad (3)$$

- **F1-Score:** Combines precision and recall as their harmonic means, offering a balanced assessment of model performance, particularly useful when handling class imbalances commonly found in medical datasets.

$$\text{F1 Score} = 2 * \frac{\text{Precision} * \text{Recall}}{\text{Precision} + \text{Recall}} \quad (4)$$

where, TP (True Positives), TN (True Negatives), FP (False Positives), and FN (False Negatives).

Fig. 4 CNN-GRU architecture

D. Hyperparameter settings and experimental setup

Hyperparameters play a key role in tuning model behavior and ensuring generalization [3]. The following were used:

- *ACO hyperparameters configuration*

ACO Parameters were set to optimize the exploration and exploitation strategies of the ants during feature subset selection process (Table 3).

- *PSO parameters configuration*

PSO configuration involved a binary implementation using a sigmoid transfer function for velocity updates and a threshold mechanism for position updates (Table 4).

- *Deep learning models configuration*

All models (CNN, GRU, CNN-GRU) were trained under uniform conditions (Table 5), using early stopping with patience of five epochs to prevent overfitting. The best-performing model weights (based on validation loss) were retained for final evaluation.

Experiments were implemented in Python using Google Colab and a local machine (Intel i5, 16 GB RAM, Windows 11). Libraries included NumPy, Pandas, Scikit-learn, and TensorFlow/Keras.

Table 3 ACO hyperparameters

Hyperparameter	Value
Number of ants	50
Number of iterations	100
Evaporation rate (ρ)	0.2
Influence of pheromone (α)	1.0
Influence of heuristic information (β)	2.0
Initial pheromone level (τ)	1.0

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Feature selection performance

The ACO and PSO algorithms were evaluated based on their ability to reduce dimensionality while maintaining classification accuracy. Both were executed with 100 iterations and a population size of 50. A RF model with 100 estimators was used as the fitness function, trained on 80% of the Breast Cancer Wisconsin dataset and tested on the remaining 20%. PSO outperformed ACO, selecting only 11 features versus ACO's 13 and achieving 100% accuracy compared to 98.2% for ACO (Table 6). PSO's superior feature subset not only reduced dimensionality but also improved classification performance, making it the preferred method for feature selection in this study. Fig. 5 illustrates the results: blue bars (left y-axis) indicate the number of features selected, and red bars (right y-axis) show the classification accuracy. PSO's higher performance confirms its effectiveness in selecting a compact and discriminative feature subset.

B. Deep learning classification performance

Using the feature subset selected by PSO, three deep learning models, GRU, CNN, and the hybrid CNN-GRU were trained under identical experimental conditions (80% training, 20% testing). Evaluation metrics included accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score (Table 7). Among the models, CNN-GRU achieved the highest scores across all metrics, effectively leveraging CNN's spatial feature extraction and GRU's temporal sequence modeling. This hybrid structure enabled more robust pattern recognition and improved generalization. Fig. 6 displays model comparisons: precision, recall, and F1-score for both benign and malignant classes are shown as bars, while the line plot represents overall accuracy.

Table 4 PSO hyperparameters

Hyperparameter	Value
Number of particles	50
Number of iterations	100
Inertia weight (w)	0.72
Cognitive coefficient (c_1)	1.49
Social coefficient (c_2)	1.49

Table 5 Deep learning models hyperparameters

Hyperparameter	CNN	GRU	CNN-GRU
Number of epochs	100 (with early stopping criteria)	100 (with early stopping criteria)	100 (with early stopping criteria)
Early stopping	Patience of 5 epochs (based on validation)	Patience of 5 epochs (based on validation)	Patience of 5 epochs (based on validation)
Batch size	16	16	16
Optimizer	Adam	Adam	Adam
Loss function	Categorical-cross entropy	Categorical-cross entropy	Categorical-cross entropy
Output activation	Softmax (2 neurons for binary classification)	Softmax (2 neurons for binary classification)	Softmax (2 neurons for binary classification)

CNN-GRU’s consistent performance highlights the advantage of combining convolutional and recurrent layers in breast cancer diagnosis.

C. Limitations of the work

While the reported results demonstrate the effectiveness of the proposed feature selection and classification framework, it is important to acknowledge some limitations. The current evaluation relied on a single 80/20 train–test split, which, although commonly used, does not fully eliminate the possibility of overfitting. A more robust validation strategy, such as k-fold cross-validation, would provide a stronger assessment of model generalization by ensuring that all data samples contribute to both training and testing across multiple folds. Incorporating such validation techniques remains an important direction for future work.

IV. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

This work evaluated ACO and PSO for feature selection in breast cancer diagnosis, followed by classification using CNN, GRU, and CNN-GRU models. PSO demonstrated superior performance, selecting fewer features and achieving perfect accuracy (100%) using a Random Forest fitness function. The retained features from PSO enabled the deep learning models to generalize effectively, with CNN-GRU delivering the best classification results. These findings emphasize the effectiveness of combining PSO with hybrid neural networks in developing accurate and computationally efficient diagnostic tools.

Table 6 Feature selection results of ACO and PSO

Algorithm	Selected features	Accuracy (%)
ACO	13	98.2
PSO	11	100

Table 7 Deep Learning Model Performance on PSO-selected features

Model	Class	Precision	Recall	F1-Score	Accuracy (%)
GRU	Benign	0.98	0.93	0.95	96.4
	Malignant	0.96	0.99	0.97	
CNN	Benign	0.98	0.98	0.98	98.2
	Malignant	0.99	0.99	0.99	
CNN-GRU	Benign	1.00	0.98	0.99	99.1
	Malignant	0.99	1.00	0.99	

Future research will address current limitations by incorporating more robust validation strategies, such as k-fold cross-validation, to further reduce the risk of overfitting. In addition, hybrid metaheuristic strategies will be explored and validation extended to larger, image-based medical datasets to enhance robustness and clinical applicability.

Fig. 5 Dual-axis histogram illustrating the comparative performance of ACO and PSO in terms of feature selection and accuracy

Fig. 6 Combined performance comparison of GRU, CNN, and CNN-GRU models trained on PSO-selected features

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

I would like to thank the Universidade Tecnológica Federal do Paraná (UTFPR) for institutional support, and express my sincere gratitude to my supervisor, Prof. Lúcia Valéria Ramos de Arruda, for her invaluable guidance and encouragement throughout this research.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

REFERENCES

1. Sung H, Ferlay J, Siegel RL, Laversanne M, Soerjomataram I, Jemal A, Bray F (2021) Global cancer statistics 2020: GLOBOCAN estimates of incidence and mortality worldwide for 36 cancers in 185 countries. *CA Cancer J Clin* 71(3):209–249. <https://doi.org/10.3322/caac.21660>
2. Murty PSRC, Kandukuri BR, Ramesh A, Varma A, Basha SM (2024) Integrative hybrid deep learning for enhanced breast cancer diagnosis: leveraging the Wisconsin Breast Cancer Database and the CBIS-DDSM dataset. *Sci Rep* 14(1):26287. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-024-74305-8>
3. Labonno MM, Asadujjaman DM, Rahman M, Tamim A, Ferdous MJ, Mahi RM (2024) Early detection and classification of breast cancer using deep learning techniques
4. Ahead F, Day C, Organization H (2024) Global cancer burden growing, amidst mounting need for services. *Bull World Health Organ* 345:185–187
5. Kim JM, Harper A, McCormack V, Sung H, Houssami N, Morgan E, Mutebi M, Garvey G, Soerjomataram I (2025) Global patterns and trends in breast cancer incidence and mortality across 185 countries. *Nat Med*
6. Quida W, Pereira S (2025) National Cancer Institute and the 2023–2025 estimate: Cancer incidence in Brazil. <https://doi.org/10.3322/caac.21660>
7. Dreyer N, Li G, Cristina A, Andrade DS (2025) Five-year overall and specific survival of breast cancer in great Cuiaba (MT), Brazil. *Rev Bras Epidemiol* 1–8
8. Kourou K, Exarchos TP, Exarchos KP, Karamouzis MV, Fotiadis DI (2015) Machine learning applications in cancer prognosis and prediction. *Comput Struct Biotechnol J* 13:8–17. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.csbj.2014.11.005>
9. Gite S, et al. (2023) Textual feature extraction using ant colony optimization for hate speech classification. *Big Data Cogn Comput* 7(1). <https://doi.org/10.3390/bdcc7010045>
10. Naseer A, Shahzad W, Ellahi A (2018) A hybrid approach for feature subset selection using ant colony optimization and multi-classifier ensemble. *Int J Adv Comput Sci Appl* 9(1):306–313. <https://doi.org/10.14569/IJACSA.2018.090142>
11. Xue B, Zhang M, Browne WN, Yao X (2016) A survey on evolutionary computation approaches to feature selection. *IEEE Trans Evol Comput* 20(4):606–626. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TEVC.2015.2504420>
12. Leoshchenko S, Oliinyk A, Subbotin S, Kolpakova T (2024) Implementation of swarm intelligence methods for preprocessing in neuroevolution synthesis. *CEUR Workshop Proc* 3702:438–448
13. Junior AHGL, Celestino J, Campos G (2024) D-ACO/GA: A bio-inspired strategy for feature selection in anomaly traffic detection in smart Internet of Things environments. *Int Conf Inf Netw*:47–52. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICOIN59985.2024.10572083>
14. Guyon I, Elisseeff A (2003) An introduction to variable and feature selection. *J Mach Learn Res* 3:1157–1182
15. Chiong R, Weise T, Michalewicz Z (2013) Variants of evolutionary algorithms for real-world applications. Springer. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-23424-8>
16. Jin Z, Shang J, Zhu Q, Ling C, Xie W, Qiang B (2020) RFRSF: Employee turnover prediction based on random forests and survival analysis. *Lect Notes Comput Sci* 12343:503–515. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-62008-0_35
17. Alam MZ, Rahman MS, Rahman MS (2019) A random forest-based predictor for medical data classification using feature ranking. *Informatics Med Unlocked* 15:100180. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.imu.2019.100180>
18. Rodriguez-Galiano VFM, Luque-Espinar JA, Chica-Olmo M (2018) Feature selection approaches for predictive modelling of groundwater nitrate pollution: An evaluation of filters, embedded and wrapper methods. *Sci Total Environ* 624:661–672
19. Ahmed SF, et al. (2023) Deep learning modelling techniques: current progress, applications, advantages, and challenges. *Artif Intell Rev* 56(11). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10462-023-10466-8>
20. LeCun Y, Bengio Y, Hinton G (2015) Deep learning. *Nature* 521(7553):436–444. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature14539>
21. Brand L, Patel A, Singh I, Brand C (2018) Real time mortality risk prediction: A convolutional neural network approach. In: *Proc Int Conf Health Informatics (BIOSTEC)* 5:463–470. <https://doi.org/10.5220/0006596204630470>
22. Na Pattalung T, Ingviya T, Chaichulee S (2021) Feature explanations in recurrent neural networks for predicting risk of mortality in intensive care patients. *J Pers Med* 11(9). <https://doi.org/10.3390/jpm11090934>
23. Kaggle (2024) Breast Cancer Wisconsin (Diagnostic) Data Set. <https://www.kaggle.com/datasets/uciml/breast-cancer-wisconsin-data>

Information of the corresponding author:

Author: Hortence Ingabire
Institute: Universidade Tecnológica Federal de Paraná (UTFPR)
Street: Rua Monsenhor Celso, 252, Centro
City: Curitiba
Country: Brazil
Email: ingahort@gmail.com